

ANALYSIS OF THE CAUSES OF UNSATISFACTORY RESULTS CARDIODILATATION IN PATIENTS WITH CARDIOSPASM AND ACHALASIA OF THE CARDIA

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Abstract. Cardiospasm and achalasia of the cardia belong to the group of neuromuscular diseases, which, according to statistics, account for up to 21% of all surgical pathologies of the esophagus, inferior in frequency to oncological lesions, cicatricial strictures and hernias of the esophageal orifice of the diaphragm. The aim is to study the causes of unsatisfactory results of cardiodilation in patients with cardiospasm and achalasia of the cardia. Material and methods. In the department of surgery of the esophagus and stomach of the State Institution "RSSPMCS named after academician V. Vakhidov" from 1975 to 2018, 947 patients with achalasia of the cardia were on outpatient and inpatient treatment. Results and discussions. Dilation with the Stark apparatus was performed in 36 (3.8%) cases in the 70-80 years of the last century, currently not used due to injury. Preference is given to pneumatic – 829 (87.5%) and hydro-balloon - 61 (6.4%) dilation. Oesophageal augmentation with hollow boughs was performed in 7 (0.7%) patients only with stenosing reflux esophagitis, which developed after previously undergone esophagocardiomyotomies. Conclusion. The reasons for the unsatisfactory results of minimally invasive methods of treatment of patients with achalasia of the cardia are the impossibility of dilation, failures in attempts to conduct the device through the cardia and directly unsatisfactory result of the course of expansion of the cardia.

Key words: esophagocardiomyotomy; cardiodilation; cardiospasm; achalasia of the cardia.

Relevance. Cardiospasm and achalasia of the cardia belong to the group of neuromuscular diseases, which, according to statistics, account for up to 21% of all surgical pathologies of the esophagus, inferior in frequency to oncological lesions, cicatricial strictures and hernias of the esophageal orifice of the diaphragm. Drug therapy in the treatment of patients with achalasia of the

cardia is of auxiliary importance and, as a rule, is indicated with contraindications to invasive treatment. The most effective minimally invasive methods of treatment include cardiodilation, stenting, endoscopic administration of botulinum toxin and oral endoscopic cardiomyotomy.

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Results and discussions. Dilation with the Stark apparatus was performed in 36 (3.8%) cases in the 70-80 years of the last century, currently not used due to injury. Preference is given to pneumatic – 829 (87.5%) and hydro-balloon - 61 (6.4%) dilation. Oesophageal augmentation with hollow boughs was performed in 7 (0.7%) patients only with stenosing reflux esophagitis, which developed after previously undergone esophagocardiomyotomies.

Good results of minimally invasive methods of treatment were obtained in 606 (64%) patients, satisfactory – in 280 (29.5%), unsatisfactory – in 61 (6.4%).

The reasons for unsatisfactory results of cardiodilation

1. The impossibility of conducting minimally invasive methods of treatment is established on the basis of a comprehensive examination of patients. With severe esophagoectasia of the esophagus and cardioesophageal junction, there is a high risk of perforation of the esophagus. The use of minimally invasive methods of treatment was impossible in 22.9% (14 patients) with stage IV disease.

2. Failures in attempts to carry out the dilator through the cardia as a cause of unsatisfactory results were noted in 26.2% (16 patients). Failures occur due to pronounced cicatricial changes in the cardia against the background of spasm, as a result of which the rigidity of the cardiodylator is not enough to overcome the resistance of the cardia; due to the S-shaped deformation of the cardia, when the tip of the dilator cannot be brought to the lumen of the cardia.

3. The absence of the effect of dilation accounted for 50.8% (31 patients) of the causes of unsatisfactory results. Patients manage to carry out the dilator through the cardia, however, after repeated sessions of cardiodylation, there is no clinical improvement in the passage of food due to the complete loss of peristaltic activity of the esophageal muscles and the so-called "rubber cardia" effect, when cardia spasm occurs again immediately after dilation.

Conclusion. The reasons for the unsatisfactory results of minimally invasive methods of treatment of patients with achalasia of the cardia are the impossibility of dilation, failures in attempts to conduct the device through the cardia and directly unsatisfactory result of the course of expansion of the cardia. If cardiodilation is ineffective and impossible, surgical treatment is necessary, the operation option depends on the degree of neglect of the disease.

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